

The Sustainable Smart City - Copenhagen

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) is a tool that can contribute positively to increase mobility and thus to sustainable development. In the project, a new ITS system will be introduced in the city of Copenhagen. It takes the three sustainability dimensions seen in Figure 1, into account. An overall analysis of the project will be presented containing a detailed analysis of the system and an assessment of its effects.

Figure 1 - The 3 dimensions of Sustainability

In order to implement the ITS, three main components must be brought together to create a sustainable Smart City. These consists of ITS technologies shown in Figure 2, project assessment and the concept behind the Smart Cities. In this context, the system engineering approach is central by involving the three main components to structure and consider the issue in a suitable manner.

Figure 2 - Components of the project